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Non Interest Income's Impact on the Profitability of Kenya's Commercial Banks

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1.1 Background to the study

Noninterest income creates income by ensuring the viability of banks in the event of nonpayment of interest income. Noninterest income includes income from property rentals, asset sales, and service fees. It is unaffected by financial market cycles and the economy as they are not subject to interest rate laws and regulations. Commercial banks' primary responsibility is to act as a conduit between its clients and available financial aid. Financial institutions distribute money received from investors and borrowers in a planned way that benefits all parties. In this way, the productivity of the entire economy is greatly increased by commercial organizations.

1.1.1 Global perspective of the study

Germany's financial sector is at jeopardy, which was examined between 2002 and 2010. Bank's business model affects how noninterest revenue affects risk. Financial institutions focused on consumers need to enhance proportion of noninterest income in order to become more stable and profitable (Kohler, et al. 2013).

Banks are more stable when they are less reliant on either interest income or noninterest income. However, as they boost their non-interest revenue, investment-focused banks have become more unstable. Banks with a higher percentage of non-traditional earnings recovered more quickly following the 2007–2009 financial crises. Banks with higher revenue concentration and smaller noninterest income are less dangerous. Risk is diminished when the impacts of bank specialization are taken into consideration. It is concluded that consideration must be given to disparities in income composition when choosing relevant peers for benchmarking (Williams, 2014).

Noninterest activities by Asian banks reduce risk but, on average, do not increase profitability, according to a study by the Bank for International Settlements (BIS). The study looked at bank accounting data from 22 Asian nations and found that noninterest activities did not increase profits. Ghanaian banks have been found to engage in more interest-free activities. Smaller banks place a greater emphasis on producing noninterest income. Bank supervisors must create policies to balance the various revenue sources of banks with their potential exposures. (Amankwaa, et al. 2014).

1.1.2 Local perspective of the study

The banking sector in Kenya is governed by the Banking Act, the central bank of Kenya Act and the Companies Act. Banks are critical in the effective distribution of funds from lenders and investors, enabling parties, investors, and banks to profit. Commercial banks were named by CBK as the main sources of finance in Kenya.

For commercial banks to be profitable the process of immediate interest on deposits, interest received on loans, other securities, and net interest margins must all be taken into account. Interest rates in developing countries like South Africa and Tanzania are lower than those offered by Kenyan banks. The study aims to examine how noninterest income affects Kenyan commercial banks' bottom lines as well as their cost of funding.

1.2 Justification of the Study

The long-term viability of banking institutions is correlated with their financial strength, and maintaining profitability is the primary goal of any bank's leadership. Given the presence of commercial banks in Meru Municipality, it is necessary to determine how the profitability of Kenya's commercial banks is impacted by non-interest justified income.

1.3 Statement of the problem

Kenya's commercial banks are still struggling to meet their predicted budgets. Central Bank of Kenya (CBK) gave commercial banks instructions on how to reduce government bonds and interest rates, and bills. This caused a sustained decline in commercial banks' profits at a higher rate.

The Central Bank of Kenya's decision to lower interest rates resulted in a considerable decrease in interest income. Despite this, banks were able to grow their noninterest and other income. Banks had to broaden their non-interest income diversification efforts (Ng'endo, 2012). Fee income is income earned by banks through the sale of third-party financial goods, such as insurance and fund management fees. Fees for banks provide interest-free income in the event of high no-show rates as a way to ensure liquidity. These sources of income include commissions from the sales of third party financial goods.

In order to control profitability and income volatility, banks have significantly increased their diversification towards noninterest revenues. DeYoung and Roland (2001) found that banks that predominantly engaged in businesses that produced interest-free revenue did not experience greater average returns on shares. Muturi Ambuka and Muturi (2018) claim that the average bank's risk/reward trade-off is enhanced by the extension to noninterest revenue. Stiroh (2006) came to the contrary conclusion that banks that predominantly engaged in businesses that produced interest-free revenue did not experience greater average returns on shares.

1.4 Research objectives

The objectives of the study are outlined in this section.

1.4.1 The general objectives

The overall goal of this study will be to investigate how noninterest income affects the profitability of commercial banks in Kenya.

1.4.2 Specific objectives of the study

The study's precise objectives will be as follows:

- i. To ascertain how bank fees and commissions affect Kenya's commercial banks' profitability.
- ii. To ascertain the effect of trade income on the Kenyan commercial banks' profitability.
- iii. To ascertain how foreign exchange revenues affect Kenya's commercial banks' profitability.
- iv. To ascertain how other bank revenues affect Kenya's commercial banks' profitability.

1.5 Scope of the study

The research effort will focus on 42 commercial banks that have been granted licenses by the Central Bank of Kenya. As of the close of business on December 31, 2020, the financial institutions that will make up the analysis units of the study were those that were still in operation. Secondary data is acquired from sources such as the National Treasury, the International Monetary Fund, and the Kenya Bureau of Statistics.

1.6 Conceptual Framework

A conceptual framework is a group of overarching concepts and guidelines used to organize a future presentation. A theoretical foundation is an instrument that helps the researcher better understand the topic at hand. It is a component of the schedule for the evaluated, tested, confirmed, and applied circumstances from each inquiry. Noninterest income affects commercial banks' profitability. This study identified these variables as independent variables. They include the effects of bank charges and commissions on profitability. Foreign exchange earnings on profitability and other bank revenues are also important. Figure 1 below shows how these factors affect bank profitability.

1.7 Research Design

The overall approach used to gather data helpful for reaching research aims is known as research design. Dawson, 2009: Dawson explains and defends the approach and research techniques adopted. It serves as a blueprint by outlining all the crucial portions of the research endeavor and how the goals will be met. Polit, Beck and Polit, research design (2003), is the overall strategy to find answers to the topics under investigation.

A research design is a set of guidelines for data collection and analysis that aims to strike a balance between procedural effectiveness and relevance to the study goal. A research plan acknowledges the general study purpose, the body of literature, and the research methodologies that have been selected. The research design ensures that all of the research operations go smoothly and that the study is as pertinent as feasible.

Lavrakas Kothari (2004) defined descriptive research as a statistical analysis that identifies and explains trends in the study population of the research topic. According to Richey & Klein, the descriptive research method can be used successfully to establish a connection between two variables. For this study of non-financial companies listed on East African stock exchanges, descriptive research was successfully used in projects by Ngigi (2009) and Ndichu (2014).

Saeed B. Moodley and Saeed (2010) used a descriptive research design to explore supply chains and risk management ideas in the oil industry. Saeed also looked at the connection between worker contentment and customer satisfaction in Telkom South Africa's service organization. According to Lempert, TSCs designs are some of the finest for correlation experiments. Olweny Baltagi Ogboi & Unuafe (2013) examines the impact of noninterest income on Kenyan commercial banks' profitability operating from 2012 to 2021. The panel approach generates more meaningful data by combining cross-sectional observations with time series variables, increasing efficiency, and increasing degrees of freedom.

1.8 Target Population

The initial target group for the study is the institutional cadre, which consists of commercial banks in Kenya. The second tier of audience will be the executives of the 42 commercial banks as of December 31, 2020. A population is any collection of discrete objects, which may be unlimited or finite. There will be a total of 41

commercial banks and 1 mortgage bank by the end of December 2020. Of the 10,390 senior workers working in Kenya's banking industry, 20% are in senior management. The Central Bank of Kenya is regarded as the most trustworthy source of information regarding the banking sector.

There will be two distinct populations in this investigation. The target audience and the accessible population both exist. The "accessible population" describes the group of people to which a researcher can apply his or her findings (Castilo, 2009). The "target audience" consists of all executives from 20 Kenyan commercial banks that were arbitrarily chosen.

1.9 Data Collection Instruments

Data gathering is the structured process of acquiring meaningful information about sub-problems within a research field (Burns et al., 2010). The analysis looked at secondary information that was taken from the CBK and the Statistical Bulletin. Data gathering includes participant observation, interviews, focus group discussions, narratives, and case studies.

2.0 Data Processing and Analysis

The investigator planned the data using the Microsoft Excel application to help operationalize the study variables. The analysis of the data was conducted using STATA software version 17.0. It features a point-and-click user interface and a command syntax that make it very simple to use. Additionally, it simplifies the creation of data plots, graphs, and reports.

2.1 Statistical Models Specification

Montgomery (1991) defined data analysis as the meticulous study of obtained information in a planned and well-organized fashion. Baltagi (1995) employed a long-run or static model to forecast the effect of bank fees and commissions, trading earnings, foreign exchange earnings, and other banking earnings on commercial bank profitability in the Kenyan setting.

Berger et al research's (2010) ROE variables. The independent variables and computed profitability values (ROA & ROE) of each bank for the years 2012–2021 are dependent on the model, according to the researchers.

$$ROE_{i,t} = f(BFC, TIGSOI, FEIG/L, OIRD) \quad (i)$$

$$ROA_{i,t} = f(BFC, TIGSOI, FEIG/L, OIRD) \quad (ii)$$

The panel data were specified as follows after linearization and parameterization, during which the variables were changed to natural logarithms:

$$ROE_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BFC_{i,t} + \beta_2 TIGSOI_{i,t} + \beta_3 FEIG/L_{i,t} + \beta_4 OIRD_{i,t} + \epsilon_{it} \quad (iii)$$

$$ROA_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BFC_{i,t} + \beta_2 TIGSOI_{i,t} + \beta_3 FEIG/L_{i,t} + \beta_4 OIRD_{i,t} + \epsilon_{it} \quad (iv)$$

The error term is an illustration of confounding, residual, or values not taken into account by the regression model for banks I at time t. BFC, TIGSOI, FEIG/L, and OIRD are the bank commissions and fees, trading

income, foreign exchange income, other banking income, and other variables, and 0 is the regression constant or intercept.

2.2 Panel Data Regression Model Estimation

Measuring the panel model equations poses the risk of generating ineffective, inconsistent, and biased estimates when any or all of the assumptions of the conventional linear regression model are violated. Barrowclough and Baddeley (2009) and integrated into the estimated error term, panel data occasionally show group effects. Panel data models, which can be either fixed or random effects models, allow for heterogeneity between the numerous panel units and usually depict relationship conditions over time that are significantly heterogeneity-limited (Baum, 2006).

2.2.1 Fixed or Random Effects Model

According to Baum (2006), individual-specific effects are measured or parameterized as additional, random distractions. The random effects model allowed researchers to estimate some variables that were removed and fixed over time. Trivedi and Cameron state that in a model with fixed effects, commercial bank unobserved effects are allowed to correlate with the explanatory variables or there is a restricted endogeneity allowance (2009).

2.2.2 Pre-Estimation and Post-Estimation Diagnostic Tests

Pooled OLS is altered when a unique sample is selected for every panel data period. Wooldridge (2012) describes how samples with comparable individual characteristics are observed throughout several time periods. Galvao et al. 2013 used FEM or SEM to estimate the model over a lengthy period of time. Various post-estimation diagnostics were developed to evaluate the estimation dependability level.

Panel Hausman Test

Wooldridge: The Hausman test was used to distinguish between REM with random effects and FEM with fixed effects. The null hypothesis for the test was that the regressors and individual heterogeneity are strictly exogenous. Given the distribution of the random and fixed effects model, the behavior of individual-specific effects, and the heterogeneity of results, the null hypothesis signifies consistency of the FEM specifications.

Panel Unit Root Test

The Levin-Lin-Chu test was applied in the current investigation. Time-series stationarity was vital to consider because estimating time-series data was based on variable stationarity. Gujarati (2003) came to the conclusion that estimating models without taking the peculiarities of non-stationarity data into consideration will ultimately result in misleading findings.

Multi-collinearity

As a diagnostic test to pre-estimate multicollinearity, the study's correlation matrix was used. Wooldridge (2012) says there is a substantial correlation between two or more independent variables. Cooper and Schindler (2013) say the correlation coefficient should be adjusted when it rises beyond 0.8. There are times when coefficients have enormous standard errors, possibly with strange magnitudes.

Bera-Jarque Normality Tests

The essential premise of CLRM, that the error component is normally distributed and its variance is constant, serves as the foundation for the reasoning behind the significance tests, which include t-tests and standard error.

The error component of CLRM is constant and regularly distributed. The null hypothesis was rejected, and model t-tests and standard errors could not be used to assess the significance of the coefficients in the models. The data were converted into their natural logarithms by the researcher and estimated using reliable standard errors.

Likelihood Ratio (LR) Test of Heteroskedasticity.

Since the error term has a constant variance, CLRM assumes that it is homoscedastic. Without taking heteroscedasticity into account, running a regression model would produce unbiased parameter estimates but inaccurate or biased standard errors.

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